

Thermal, Spectral and Magnetic Studies of Fluorenone Anthranilic Acid Complexes of Manganese(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

K JOBY THOMAS and GEETHA PARAMESWARAN*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635

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Fluorenoneanthranilic acid, a novel Schiff base, forms 1 : 1 complexes with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} acetates. All the complexes are found to be non-electrolytes in nitrobenzene, and octahedral structures are assigned to them based on electronic and magnetic data. Ir studies reveal that the complexes are formed by the replacement of the hydrogen atom of the COOH group by the metal with the azomethine nitrogen coordinating to the metal. The thermal decomposition of the $[ML(Ac)(H_2O)_3]$ chelates was studied by TG and DTA techniques. The mechanism of the decomposition has been established from TG data. The kinetic parameters, namely, activation energy (E), pre-exponential factor (A) and entropy of activation (ΔS) were calculated from TG curves using mechanistic and non-mechanistic equations. On the basis of our findings, the relative thermal stabilities of the three chelates have been evaluated.

Metal complexes of Schiff bases are known for their pharmacological applications¹. Their activity has frequently been thought to be due to their ability to chelate trace metals. Wendlandt *et al.*² and Scency *et al.*³ studied the thermal properties of metal chelates with different types of complexing ligands. A few workers⁴ have done such studies on the thermal decomposition and kinetics of metal chelates with azomethine ligands. In continuation of our earlier work on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases⁵, we report here the preparation, characterisation and thermoanalytical data of three transition metal complexes of a novel Schiff base, fluorenoneanthranilic acid (FAA) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Analysis of data : The TG curve for $[MnL(Ac)(H_2O)_3]$ exhibited a two-stage decomposition pattern and those of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} exhibited three-stage decomposition pattern. The second stage represents the major decomposition step in the case of the Ni and Co complexes. Mass loss considerations and X-ray diffraction data confirmed the products to be the corresponding oxides.

Evaluation of the reaction mechanism by non-isothermal methods has been discussed by Sestak and Berggren⁶ and Satava⁷. The procedure is based on the assumption that the non-isothermal reaction proceeds isothermally in an infinitesimal time interval, so that the rate can be expressed by an Arrhenius type equation,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A e^{-E/RT} f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor, t the time and $f(\alpha)$ depends on the mechanism of the process. For a linear heating rate (ϕ), $dT/dt = \phi$ and substitution into eqn. (1) gives

$$\frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = \int_0^T \frac{A}{\phi} e^{-E/RT} dT \quad (2)$$

Integration of the left-hand-side of eqn. (2) gives

$$\int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = g(\alpha) = \int_0^T \frac{A}{\phi} e^{-E/RT} dT \quad (3)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is the integral form of $f(\alpha)$. A series of $f(\alpha)$ forms are proposed and the mechanism is obtained from that which gives the best representation of the experimental data. For evaluating kinetic parameters from the mechanistic equations given by Satava, Coats and Redfern⁸ equation was used in the general form,

$$\ln \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} = \ln \frac{AR}{\phi E} - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (4)$$

and the various $g(\alpha)$ values were substituted. This has been recommended to be one of the best solutions by several authors⁹.

Alongwith the mechanistic equations, two non-mechanistic methods suggested by Coats and Redfern and Horowitz and Metzger¹⁰ were also used for comparison. The reaction order can easily be estimated by comparing their values using $n = 0.33, 0.5, 0.66$ and 1 in eqns. (5) and (6),

$$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n} / (1 - n) T^2 \text{ vs } 1/T \text{ for } n \neq 1 \quad (5)$$

$$\log[-\log(1 - \alpha)] / T^2 \text{ vs } 1/T \text{ for } n = 1 \quad (6)$$

Results and Discussion

Molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility and analytical data are presented in Table 1. The complexes exhibit molar conductances in the range $2-10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in nitrobenzene, indicating non-electrolytic nature. Octahedral geometry is confirmed by their magnetic moment data.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Metal%: Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B M.	Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
[MnL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃] (Pink)	13.01 (12.54)	6.53	0.8
[CoL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃] (Brown)	12.88 (12.52)	4.91	1.8
[NiL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃] (Green)	12.11 (11.80)	3.52	1.5

The infrared spectrum of the ligand shows a band of medium intensity at about 1692 cm^{-1} and a strong band at 1577 cm^{-1} . The first

band may be attributed to the carbonyl stretching frequency of the carboxylate group¹¹. A shift of this band to lower frequencies indicates chelation of the ligand to the metal atom through the carbonyl oxygen. The sharp band at 1577 cm^{-1} (C=N) of the Schiff base residue shifts to lower frequencies at $1536, 1529$ and 1532 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating a reduction of electron density in the azomethine linkage at the nitrogen coordinated to the metal ion¹². In the chelates, the presence of coordinated water is confirmed by the observation of a broad band at 3300 cm^{-1} .

However, conclusive evidence regarding the bonding of nitrogen and oxygen is provided by the occurrence of ir bands at 419 (M-N) and $\approx 572 \text{ (M-O)}$ in the metal complexes¹³. The ir data suggest that FAA behaves as bidentate chelating agent for the metal ions, coordinating through the carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The probable general structure of the complexes is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Triaquofluorenoneanthranilatoacetatomanganese(II)/cobalt(II)/nickel(II).

Electronic spectrum of the Schiff base is characterised by two intense bands lying at 30769 and 33783 cm^{-1} . During the complex formation a red-shift is observed for these bands which indicates the involvement of Schiff base in coordination. In addition, the spectra of the complexes are characterised by a strong band at 33000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the charge transfer transition.

The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex revealed a band at 24800 cm^{-1} which support the presence of Mn^{II} in an octahedral geometry¹⁴.

The purple colour of $[\text{CoL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ is suggestive of octahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex is characterised by two bands at 9 500–10 526 and 20 000–22 000 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions¹⁵. The Ni^{II} complex also exhibits three *d-d* transitions at 10 000, 15 503 and 23 529 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions¹⁶.

The TG curve for $[\text{MnL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ gives a two-stage decomposition pattern which is supported by the DTA data. The first stage represents the loss of 3 H_2O molecules and the ligand moiety above 230°. According to Nikolaev *et al.*¹⁷, water eliminated above 150° can be considered as coordinated water. The second stage represents the loss of the acetate part. DTA curve gives well-defined peak in the appropriate region. The overall loss of mass from the curve is 84% while the theoretical loss in mass for the conversion of $[\text{MnL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ to Mn_3O_4 is 83.62%. In the case of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} chelates, a three-stage decomposition pattern is observed. The main decomposition stage is represented by DTA peaks at 340 and 370° respectively. The mass loss at the end of this stage as read from the TG curve is 68.5 and 67% respectively.

The thermal data for the metal chelates are given in Table 2. Data from independent pyrolytic experiments are also given in this table. The kinetic parameters calculated from TG data for

the nine mechanistic equations are given in Table 3. The corresponding values E , A , ΔS and r from non-mechanistic equations (Coats-Redfern and Horowitz-Metzger) and the appropriate mechanistic equations are given in Table 4. The cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes lose two water molecules at about 180°. The E values obtained for this step by various non-mechanistic methods (Coats-Redfern = 18.77, 13.81 kJ mol^{-1} ; Horowitz-Metzger = 26.36, 21.28 kJ mol^{-1}) are comparable to that for other similar hydrated complexes of transition metals¹⁸. The activation energy obtained for the main decomposition stages of both complexes are also comparable to those of coordination compounds of 3*d* transition metals having similar structures¹⁹.

Initial decomposition temperature and inflection temperatures have been used to determine the thermal stability of the metal chelates. In the present course of studies, based on observations made by earlier workers²⁰, the relative thermal stabilities of the metal chelates can be given as $[\text{CoL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \approx [\text{NiL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3] < [\text{MnL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$.

Decomposition kinetics : From Tables 3 and 4, it can be seen that more than one equation gives good linear curves with high correlation coefficient. It thus becomes difficult to assign the reaction mechanisms unequivocally from the linearity of the curve alone. In such cases, some authors chose the function $g(\alpha)$ which gives the kinetic parameters in agreement with those obtained

 TABLE 2—THERMAL DECOMPOSITION DATA OF $[\text{MnL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$, $[\text{CoL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ and $[\text{NiL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$

Compd.	Stage	Temp. range in TG °C	Peak temp. in TG °C	Peak temp in DTA °C	Loss of mass (%)			Probable assignment
					From TG	Theoretical	From pyrolysis (total mass loss)	
$[\text{MnL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$	1	60–430	315	320	76.00	75.55	–	Loss of 3 H_2O + L
	2	430–800	no peaks		8.00	8.07	–	Loss of acetate
							83.19	
$[\text{CoL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$	1	40–210	165	180	7.50	7.66	–	Loss of 2 H_2O
	2	210–420	330	340	68.50	67.25	–	Loss of 1 H_2O + L
	3	420–900	880	900br	6.00	8.02	–	Loss of acetate
							83.10	
$[\text{NiL}(\text{Ac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$	1	50–200	160	150	7.50	7.66	–	Loss of 2 H_2O
	2	200–450	350	370	67.00	67.28	–	Loss of 1 H_2O + L
	3	450–900	890	900br	9.00	9.16	–	Loss of acetate
							83.20	

TABLE 3—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF [MnL(Ac)(H₂O)₃], [CoL(Ac)(H₂O)₃] and [NiL(Ac)(H₂O)₃] FROM TG USING MECHANISTIC EQUATIONS

Compd.	Parameter*	Mechanistic equations								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
[MnL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃]										
I Stage	E	174.99	178.91	182.96	180.26	88.73	39.58	23.19	85.69	86.69
	A	8.37 × 10 ¹¹	1.01 × 10 ¹²	5.54 × 10 ¹¹	8.03 × 10 ¹¹	6.54 × 10 ⁴	3.07	8.51 × 10 ⁻²	1.62 × 10 ⁴	1.37 × 10 ⁴
	ΔS	-22.31	-20.81	-25.74	-30.77	-158.48	-241.37	-271.21	-170.08	-171.50
	r	0.9171	0.9161	0.9151	0.9157	0.9060	0.8861	0.8597	0.9073	0.9068
[CoL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃]										
I Stage	E	24.86	33.17	44.71	36.94	25.14	8.99	3.61	15.95	18.78
	A	1.41	1.34 × 10	1.49 × 10 ²	1.09 × 10	3.82	1.34 × 10 ⁻²	1.16 × 10 ⁻³	6.89 × 10 ⁻²	1.31 × 10 ⁻¹
	ΔS	-245.28	-226.56	-206.56	-228.33	-237.01	-284.01	-304.43	-270.41	-265.06
II Stage	r	0.9637	0.9665	0.9681	0.9671	0.9602	0.9270	0.8320	0.9526	0.9559
	E	121.13	121.98	122.84	122.27	57.28	24.06	12.99	56.63	56.85
	A	2.34 × 10 ⁶	1.44 × 10 ⁶	3.94 × 10 ⁵	3.43 × 10 ⁵	3.22 × 10	5.39 × 10 ⁻²	4.61 × 10 ⁻³	1.37 × 10	9.62
II Stage	ΔS	-128.92	-132.95	-143.75	-144.88	-222.03	-275.23	-295.66	-229.18	-232.07
	r	0.9929	0.9928	0.9926	0.9927	0.9913	0.9878	0.9817	0.9915	0.9914
	[NiL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃]									
I Stage	E	18.45	25.21	34.85	28.35	19.19	5.98	1.58	11.45	13.81
	A	1.83 × 10 ⁻¹	1.18	8.22	8.19 × 10 ⁻¹	5.96 × 10 ⁻¹	3.93 × 10 ⁻³	2.92 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.47 × 10 ⁻²	2.54 × 10 ⁻²
	ΔS	-262.29	-246.77	-230.64	-249.82	-252.46	-294.11	-315.88	-283.27	-278.62
	r	0.9846	0.9864	0.9859	0.9864	0.9788	0.9521	0.7880	0.9778	0.9788
II Stage	E	106.78	107.81	108.85	108.16	50.09	20.19	10.22	49.31	49.57
	A	3.31 × 10 ⁴	2.09 × 10 ⁴	5.89 × 10 ³	5.03 × 10 ³	3.48	1.50 × 10 ⁻²	1.67 × 10 ⁻³	1.44	1.02
	ΔS	-164.61	-168.42	-178.96	-180.28	-240.80	-286.13	-304.39	-248.12	-250.97
	r	0.9983	0.9982	0.9981	0.9982	0.9980	0.9977	0.9971	0.9981	0.9980

*E in kJ mol⁻¹, A in s⁻¹; ΔS in JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

TABLE 4—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF [MnL(Ac)(H₂O)₃], [CoL(Ac)(H₂O)₃] AND [NiL(Ac)(H₂O)₃] FROM TG USING NON-MECHANISTIC EQUATION*

Compd.	E	Coats-Redfern			Horowitz-Metzger				Mechanistic equation followed				Order of reaction (n)
		A	ΔS	r	E	A	ΔS	r	E	A	ΔS	r	
[MnL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃]													
I Stage	84.69	2.58 × 10 ⁴	-166.20	0.9077	98.92	5.57 × 10 ⁵	-140.62	0.9278	85.69	1.63 × 10 ⁴	-170.05	0.9073	Equation VII: 1/3 Phase boundary reaction, cylindrical symmetry
[CoL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃]													
I Stage	25.14	3.82	-237.01	0.9602	32.79	1.80 × 10	-224.11	0.9772	25.14	3.82	-237.01	0.9602	Equation V: 1
II Stage	56.42	2.59 × 10	-223.85	0.9916	78.51	3.11 × 10 ³	-183.97	0.9935	56.63	1.37 × 10	-229.17	0.9915	Equation VIII: 1/3 Phase boundary reaction, cylindrical symmetry
[NiL(Ac)(H ₂ O) ₃]													
I Stage	19.19	5.96 × 10 ⁻¹	-252.46	0.9788	26.76	4.80	-235.10	0.9920	19.19	5.96 × 10 ⁻¹	-252.46	0.9788	Equation V: 1 Mampel equation
II Stage	49.05	2.71	-242.87	0.9981	65.53	8.76 × 10	-213.94	0.9998	49.31	1.44	-248.12	0.9981	Equation VII: 1/3 Phase boundary reaction, cylindrical symmetry

*E in kJ mol⁻¹; A in s⁻¹; ΔS in JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

by the numerical method. In the present case, it is observed that for the first stage of decomposition of the Mn^{II} complex and the second stage of decomposition of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, the E , A and ΔS values obtained from the Coats-Redfern equation with $n = 1/3$ are in good agreement with those obtained for the R_2 mechanism based on a phase boundary reaction, cylindrical symmetry. For the first stage of decomposition of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, the E , A and ΔS values obtained from Coats-Redfern method with $n = 1$ agree with those from the Mampel equation which is based on random nucleation.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared from fluorenone and anthranilic acid in ethanol medium following the reported procedure²¹. Fluorenone (1.80 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was mixed with anthranilic acid (1.37 g, 0.01 mol) and was refluxed for 5 h. On cooling, the resulting yellowish brown crystals (90%) were purified by crystallisation from methanol and characterised on the basis of analytical and spectral data, m.p. 95° (Found : C, 80.68; H, 4.21; N, 5.14. $C_{20}H_{13}NO_2$ calcd. for : C, 80.27; H, 4.35; N, 4.68%).

General method for preparing the complexes : A mixture of methanolic solution (10 ml) of the metal acetate (0.01 mol) and a methanolic solution (15 ml) of the ligand (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 5 h and the resulting solid was washed with methanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

The molar conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene at a concentration of $\sim 10^{-4} M$, was measured at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge with a dip type cell and a platinum electrode. Thermal analysis was carried out using a Schimadzu thermal analyser in static air maintaining the rate of heating at $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. Computational work was done with a Horizon III mini-computer using the programming language Fortran. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann IR-12 spectrophotometer and solid state electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Hitachi-220 spectrophotometer. The magnetic

measurement was performed at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $[HgCo(NCS)_4]$ as a calibration standard.

References

1. W. W. WENDLANDT, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1957, **17**, 428.
2. G. P. ASCENZO and W. W. WENDLANDT, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1969, **1**, 423; *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **50**, 79; F. C. CHANG and W. W. WENDLANDT, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1971, **2**, 293; D. L. PERRY, C. VAZ and W. W. WENDLANDT, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1974, **9**, 76.
3. C. G. SCENCY, J. O. HILL and R. J. MAGEE, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1975, **11**, 301; C. G. SCENCY, J. F. SMITH, J. O. HILL and R. J. MAGEE, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1976, **9**, 415.
4. M. LEHTINEN and K. MAIRE, *Acta Pharm. Fenn.*, 1981, **90**, 187; K. N. JOHRI and B. S. ARORA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1982, **54**, 237; L. PARDESHI and R. A. BHOBE, *Acta Cienca Indica*, 1982, **8**, 178; L. PARDESHI and R. A. RHOBE, *Acta Cienca Indica*, 1983, **9**, 18.
5. N. L. MARY and G. PARAMESWARAN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1991, **185**, 345; *Synth. React. Inorg. Meta-Org. Chem.*, 1993, **23**, 1209; S. LALY and G. PARAMESWARAN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1990, **43**, 168.
6. J. SESTAK and G. BERGGREN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1971, **3**.
7. V. SATAVA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1971, **2**, 2.
8. A. W. COATS and J. P. REDFERN, *Nature (London)*, 1964, **201**, 68.
9. M. D. JUDD and M. T. POPE, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1972, **4**, 31; J. ZSAKO, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1975, **8**, 349.
10. J. H. HOROWITZ and G. METZGER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 1464.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1966.
12. R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 33.
13. J. R. FERRARE, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
14. S. N. PODDAR, K. DEY, J. HALDER and S. C. NATHSARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 743.
15. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 887.
16. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, London, 1968.
17. A. V. NIKOLAEV, V. A. LOGVINENKO and L. I. MYACHINA, "Thermal Analysis", Academic, New York, 1969, p. 779.
18. K. SINGH and S. MITRA, 'Proceedings of the Sixth National Symposium on Thermal Analysis', ITAS, Delhi, 1987, 111.8, 24; L. S. PRABHU, MIRASHI, S. R. NAIK and J. K. KHOJE, 'Proceedings of the Seventh National Symposium on Thermal Analysis', ITAS, Srinagar, 1989, 111.6, 92.
19. S. VATSALA and G. PARAMESWARAN, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1986, **31**, 883; R. S. NAIDU, E. N. RAO, R. RUBY and K. G. MALLIKARJUN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1988, **131**, 299; 1989, **140**, 97.
20. V. SESHAGIRI and S. B. RAO, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **262**, 275; R. S. NAIDU and R. R. NAIDU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15**, 652.
21. R. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT and A. CHAKRAVORTHY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 83.

